

Counselling Strategies for Reducing Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) among Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers State

Dimkpa Marilyn & Prof. C. Agi

Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling
Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt

Abstract

The study examined counselling strategies for reducing spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Three specific objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Rivers State. The population of the study was 30,889 comprising 333 school guidance counsellors and 30,556 students. The sample size was 450 which comprises 420 students and 30 school guidance counsellors in senior secondary schools in Rivers State obtained using multistage sampling technique. The instrument used for the study was a self-designed instrument titled “Counselling Strategies for Reducing Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) among Senior Secondary School Students (CSRSSTD)”. The instrument was structured in a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was validated and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.87, 0.77, and 0.89 which indicated that the instrument was reliable. The data gathered through research instruments were analysed using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that utilization of behavioural counselling, risk reduction counselling and preventive counselling are identified as the strategies that can help reduce the spread of sexually transmitted diseases at high extent. The study recommended that school administrators encourage guidance counsellors in organization of counselling programmes that are tailored towards discouraging unhealthy sexual behaviours of students. This can help students develop a healthy sexual culture thereby reducing their vulnerability to sexually transmitted diseases.

Keywords: Counselling Strategies, Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs), Spread, Students

INTRODUCTION

Sexually Transmitted Diseases is a major health issue in sub-Saharan African. Sub-Saharan Africa ranks first in STD yearly incidence compared to other world regions. Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) as the name implies are diseases that are contacted through sexual intercourse. These diseases can also be contacted in ways other than sexual contacts such as blood transfusion or sharp objects. Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are infections spread by sexual contact with someone who is infected. STDs, or sexually transmitted infections (STIs), are caused by bacteria, parasites, or viruses (World Health Organisation, 2011). A sexually transmitted infection may pass from person to person in blood, semen, or vaginal and other bodily fluids.

There are various examples of sexually transmitted diseases that are commonly found in Africa. The World Health Organization has estimated that every year in Africa there are 3.5 million cases of syphilis, 15 million cases of chlamydial disease, 16 million cases of gonorrhoea, and 30 million cases of trichomoniasis (Gerbase & Mertens, 1998). The prevalence of STDs in Africa has predisposed the population to serious public health issues, contributing significantly to population morbidity and mortality (Shewarega, et al., 2022). When untreated, STIs can cause significant morbidity, particularly for women, leading to complications such as pelvic inflammatory disease, ectopic pregnancy, infertility, pregnancy complications, and newborn

infection. Furthermore, STI-induced genital inflammation and genital HIV shedding can increase risks of HIV acquisition and transmission, even when the STI is asymptomatic (Warr, et al. 2019; Reekie, et al. 2019).

According to Temin, et al., (1999) the spread of STD among adolescents is alarming as many studies reported high level of premarital sexual activities among adolescents in Nigeria. Although, no proper record exists on the statistics of STD prevalence among adolescents in Nigeria, it is estimated that they account for between 15 and 30 percent of all reported cases of infections and often times, due to the exorbitant cost of procuring treatment, many of those infected do not seek health care from qualified medical personnel (Alade, 2023). However, adolescents are at high risk for acquiring sexually transmitted diseases. Research has demonstrated that a large percentage of sexually active teenagers have multiple sex partners (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, 2001) and that a greater number of sex partners is associated with an increased risk of having a sexually transmitted disease (STD) (Mosure, et al. 1997). Similarly, in the study of Rosenberg, et al. (1999) it was found that that having greater numbers of concurrent partners was associated with higher STD risk, independent of the number of partners. There are several reasons why, given the same number of partners, having concurrent partners could increase an individual's risk of

being exposed to or acquiring an STD. Individuals with concurrent partners may increase the number of people to whom they are connected at any given time, increasing their risk of exposure to an STD as well as reinfection from an untreated sex partner.

Over the years, a number of health care programmes has been organized to reduce the incidence of sexually transmitted diseases, however less knowledge and awareness regarding the mode of transmission and spread continue to sponsor the increase in the spread of sexually transmitted diseases. Rai, Aggarwal and Kandpa (2011) added that judgmental attitudes of the service providers, who often lack counselling skills, are the barriers that limit access to services so assessing their knowledge, attitude and practice about sexually transmitted infections will provide an insight to the reproductive sexual health needs of adolescents. Hence, there is need for proper counselling to aid the effectiveness of health care programmes against the spread of sexually transmitted diseases particularly among adolescents.

Good counselling is important in helping people with concerns about sexuality, STI and HIV (International Planned Parenthood Federation, 2002). It is important that counselling plays active role in discouraging the spread of sexually transmitted diseases. This is because many people feel unable to talk about them having STDs due to embarrassment or fear of rejection. If they do, they may not receive the emotional support, information and skills they require to thrive. Fears about the future, guilt, anger and despair may overwhelm them. Using counselling strategies can help discourage these acts by providing the support required for victims to reduce the spread among non-victims.

Behavioural counselling is a stratagem counsellors utilize to bring about behavioural adjustment in a client. Behavioural counselling is rooted in the principles of behaviourism, which focuses on the idea that our behaviours can be structured based on our environment. The goal is to reinforce desirable behaviors and eliminate unwanted ones (Agi & Temisa, 2023). The techniques do not focus on clients achieving insights into their behaviour; rather the focus is just on changing the behaviour. Empirical evidence have shown that behavioral counseling is effective at reducing STI transmission in those at higher risk, reducing STI acquisition by as much as 30% (Jin, 2020). The author further added that behavioral counseling increases condom use and safer sex practices for adolescents. Various attitudes and practices among young adolescents that aid the spread of sexually transmitted diseases can be discouraged by seeking to adjust their behaviours. For instance, attitudes towards multiple partners, sharing of sharp objects, indiscriminate sexual intercourse, maintaining personal hygiene among others can be

discourages among adolescents through behavioural counselling.

Risk reduction counseling is another counselling strategy that could help reduce the risk of sexually transmitted diseases among young adolescents. In this counselling strategy, counsellors expose youngsters to various risks that could make them vulnerable to sexually transmitted diseases. Young adults are also exposed to diverse sources of influence (multiple sexual partners, lack of condom use) transecting different levels of causation (WHO, 2006). The knowledge of the non-HIV causes of STDs is still lacking, and the risky behaviour practiced by sexually active young adults is on the rise. These risky actions could be curbed by exposing the adolescents to potential risk of sexually transmitted diseases and means of avoidance.

Preventive counselling as the name implies is a mode of counselling aimed at preventing anticipated problems. A school-based preventive counseling program, for example, may focus on educating and providing guidance to adolescents about such issues as bullying and school violence, substance abuse, teen pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases, eating disorders, and suicide, with the goal of reducing their vulnerability to these and similar problems that often occur in this particular age group (American Psychological Association, 2018). This kind of counselling is often used to stop problems before they start or to prevent things from getting worse. Oluwole, Oyekanmi, Ogunyemi and Osanyin (2020) asserted that comprehensive sexuality education, STI and HIV pre- and post-test counselling, condom promotion and interventions targeted at key populations are preventive counselling measures geared towards reducing the spread of sexually transmitted Diseases. The prevention of STIs, especially in the regions where they are endemic, propelled mainly by heterosexual transmission, includes vaccination (for vaccine-preventable diseases) and practice of the 'ABC' approach (abstinence, be faithful to one partner and use of condom) (WHO, 2016). In the study of Oluwole et al., (2020), it was found that most of the respondents revealed that gaps exist in knowledge and preventive practices. Hence, structured counselling programme is needed to improve the knowledge and preventive practices against STI among young unmarried persons.

Statement of the Problem

Sexually Transmitted Disease has become a global phenomenon which affects many young adolescents in recent time. Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) are a major health problem affecting mostly young people in both developed and developing countries. Insufficient knowledge about STDs is a major impediment to successfully prevent the diseases among adolescent populations in developing countries. In the last two

decades sexual behavior exhibited by school adolescents and youth between 19 to 24 years has led to the emergence of several health and developmental problems among students. Among the key issues associated with these problems were unprotected sex and undesirable sexual behavior, teenage pregnancy, sexual harassment and increasing cases of prostitution (National AIDS Control Program, 2000). Despite the good intention of introducing reproductive health education in schools, the spread of sexually transmitted diseases still remains. Based on this backdrop, the study sought to determine counselling strategies for reducing spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate counselling strategies for reducing spread of sexually transmitted diseases (STDS) among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Specifically, the study will seek to;

1. Determine behavioural counselling strategies for reducing spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State
2. Determine risk reduction counselling strategies for reducing spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State
3. Determine preventive counselling strategies for reducing spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent would behavioural counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. To what extent would risk reduction counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
3. To what extent would preventive counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of counsellors and students on the extent behavioural counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of school guidance counsellors and

students on the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

3. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of school guidance counsellors and students on the extent preventive counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. This design was considered suitable for this study because it entails description of a situation as it is, using the opinion of the respondents and encourages generalization. According to Amadi (2020), descriptive survey design is concerned with obtaining responses from a population to describe a situation. The study was carried out in Rivers State. According to Onovo, et al. (2023), Rivers State is second in the rating of HIV prevalence in Nigeria. This situation made the choice of the area, suitable for this study. The population of the study involved all senior secondary school counsellors and students in Rivers State. The population of the study was 30,889 comprising 333 school guidance counsellors and 30,556 students. The senior secondary school's board (2022) states that there are 30,556 senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Taro Yamene formula was used to obtain a minimum sample size of 394. However, for convenient sample selection, the researcher decided to engage 420 students in the study through multi stage sampling technique. At first stage cluster random sampling was used to group Rivers State into three clusters namely Rivers East, Rivers West and Rivers South East. From each of the senatorial district, simple random sampling was used to select 10 senior secondary schools, making 30 schools involved in the study. Lastly, 14 students were randomly selected from each of the selected 30 secondary schools, arriving to a total of 420 students. However, 30 guidance counsellors from the selected secondary schools were also involved in the study. Hence the sample size was 450 which comprises 420 students and 30 school guidance counsellors in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The instrument used for the study was a self-designed instrument titled "Counselling Strategies for Reducing Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) among Senior Secondary School Students (CSRSSTD)". The instrument was structured in a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by two experts in guidance and counselling, from the Department of Educational Foundations, Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha. Cronbach Alpha was

considered suitable because, it tends to determine the internal consistency of the research instrument. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.87, 0.77, and 0.89 which indicated that the instrument was reliable. 450 copies of the questionnaire were administered, however only 402 copies were retrieved comprising 372 copies from students and 30 copies from guidance counsellors. The data gathered through research instruments were analysed using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Decision was made based on the benchmark mean of

2.50, that items with mean value less than 2.50 were termed “Low Extent” while those with mean values greater than or equal to 2.50 were rated “High Extent”. Hypotheses was significant when the p-value is less than the level of significance which stood at 0.05 and vice-versa.

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent would behavioural counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Table 1: Extent would Behavioural Counselling Strategies Reduce Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases among Senior Secondary School Students

S/N	Items	Guidance Counsellor= 30			Students=372		Rmk
		Mean	S.D	Rmk	Mean	S.D	
1	Interactive approach geared towards educating students on reducing the risk of STD transmission can help reduce the spread of STDs.	3.23	0.86	HE	3.56	0.65	HE
2	Personalised goals settings technique helps students reduce involvement in sexual activities in school	3.10	0.71	HE	3.29	0.67	HE
3	Enhancing students’ motivation to sexual behavioural change through motivational interviewing	3.34	1.02	HE	3.19	0.68	HE
4	Exploring students’ natural ambivalence about STDs can help determine the means to reduce the spread among students	3.20	0.69	HE	3.23	0.76	HE
5	Systematic desensitization on unhealth sexual behaviour can reduce the spread of STDs among students	3.41	0.72	HE	3.19	0.88	HE
6	Role playing on sex avoidance can help increase abstinence among students	3.17	1.02	HE	3.28	0.78	HE
7	Attaching reinforcement to students’ sexual abstinence would help reduce STD spread among secondary school students	2.61	0.73	HE	2.80	0.67	HE
Grand Mean & S.D.		3.15	0.82		3.22	0.73	

Source: Research Data, 2024

Table 1 shows mean responses of the respondents on the extent behavioural counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students. Judging from the mean displayed in table 1, it is revealed that items 1-7 have mean values ranging from 2.61-3.56 which is greater than criterion mean value of 2.50. Hence, items displayed in table 1 are behavioural counselling strategies which reduced the

spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students at high extent. The standard deviation of 0.82 and 0.73

Research Question 2: To what extent would risk reduction counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Table 2: Extent would Risk Reduction Counselling Strategies Reduce Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases among Senior Secondary School Students

S/N	Items	Guidance Counsellor= 30			Students=372		
		Mean	S.D	Rmk	Mean	S.D	Rmk
1	Exposing students to healthy protective sexual behaviours in counselling can reduce the risk of STD spreads among students	3.21	0.83	HE	3.38	0.71	HE
2	Educating students on how STDs are contacted would help identify risk of sexually transmitted diseases	3.18	1.02	HE	3.23	0.60	HE
3	Providing enlightenment on the need to use condoms during sex would reduce the spread of STDs	2.90	0.78	HE	2.79	1.02	HE
4	Encouraging abstinence from sex can reduce students' involvement in sexual activities	3.10	0.90	HE	3.74	0.87	HE
5	Discouraging multiple sexual partners among students would help reduce the spread of STD	2.98	0.78	HE	2.89	1.02	HE
6	Providing the opportunity for risk screening can help in reducing the spread of STD among students	3.11	0.67	HE	3.11	0.85	HE
Grand Mean & S.D.		3.08	0.83		3.19	0.85	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Based on the criterion mean value of 2.50, exposing students to healthy protective sexual behaviours in counselling can reduce the risk of STD spreads among students (3.21 & 3.38), educating students on how STDs are contacted would help identify risk of sexually transmitted diseases (3.18 & 3.23), providing enlightenment on the need to use condoms during sex would reduce the spread of STDs (2.90 &

2.79), encouraging abstinence from sex can reduce students' involvement in sexual activities (3.10 & 3.74), discouraging multiple sexual partners among students would help reduce the spread of STD (2.98 & 2.89), and providing the opportunity for risk screening can help in reducing the spread of STD among students (3.11 & 3.11)

Research Question 3: To what extent would preventive counselling strategies reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Table 3: Extent would Preventive Counselling Strategies Reduce Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases among Senior Secondary School Students

S/N	Items	Guidance Counsellor= 30			Students=372		
		Mean	S.D	Rmk	Mean	S.D	Rmk
1	Exposing students to preventive measures of sexually transmitted diseases can help reduce its spread	3.18	0.78	HE	3.04	0.67	HE
2	Enlightening young adolescent on the prevalence of sexually transmitted diseases in the area can reduce the spread of STDs	3.43	0.69	HE	3.23	0.69	HE
3	Promoting safer sexual practices through counselling programmes in schools would lessen spread of STDs among adolescents	3.34	1.02	HE	3.45	0.64	HE
4	Discussing sexuality and sex education with students can help encourage healthy sexual activities among students	2.90	1.01	HE	2.89	1.03	HE
5	Exposing students to healthy sexual development practices would help reduce the spread of sexually transmitted diseases	2.79	1.02	HE	2.80	1.12	HE
Grand Mean & S.D		3.13	0.90		3.08	0.83	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 revealed the extent preventive counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students, Rivers State. Based on the criterion mean value 2.50, the study found that to a high extent exposing students to preventive measures to sexually transmitted diseases (3.18 & 3.04), enlightening young adolescent on the prevalence of sexually transmitted diseases in the area can reduce their (3.43 & 3.23), promoting safer sexual practices through counselling programmes in schools (3.34 & 3.45), discussing sexuality and sex education with students can help encourage healthy sexual activities among students (2.90 & 2.89) and exposing

students to healthy sexual development practices would help reduce the spread of sexually transmitted diseases (2.79 & 2.80). The grand mean of 3.13 and 3.08 showed that preventive counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students at high extent.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of counsellors and students on the extent behavioural counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 4: z-test analysis on the Extent Behavioural Counselling Strategies Would Reduce Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases

Categories	N	Mean	S.D	df	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Guidance Counsellors	30	3.15	0.82	400	0.46	1.96	Accept
Students	372	3.22	0.73				

Research Data, 2024

Table 4 displayed z-test analysis on the extent behavioural counselling strategies would reduce spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases. Since the z-calculated value (0.46) is less than the z-critical value (1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of counsellors and students on the extent behavioural counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually

transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of school guidance counsellors and students on the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 5: z-test analysis on the Extent Risk Reduction Counselling Strategies Would Reduce Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases

Categories	N	Mean	S.D	df	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Guidance Counsellors	30	3.08	0.83	400	0.66	1.96	Accept
Students	372	3.19	0.85				

Research Data, 2024

Table 5 displayed z-test analysis on the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases. Since the z-calculated value (0.66) is less than the z-critical value (1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of counsellors and students on the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually

transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of school guidance counsellors and students on the extent preventive counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 6: z-test analysis on the Extent Preventive Counselling Strategies Would Reduce Spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases

Categories	N	Mean	S.D	df	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Guidance Counsellors	30	3.13	0.90	400	0.71	1.96	Accept
Students	372	3.08	0.83				

Research Data, 2024

Table 6 displayed z-test analysis on the extent preventive counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases. Since the z-calculated value (0.71) is less than the z-critical value (1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of counsellors and students on the extent preventive counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question 1 showed the extent to which behavioural counselling strategies would reduce spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases among senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Findings showed that interactive approach geared towards educating students on reducing the risk of STD transmission, personalised goals settings technique helps students reduce involvement in sexual activities in school, enhancing students' motivation to sexual behavioural change through motivational interviewing and exploring students' natural ambivalence about STDs can help determine the means to reduce the spread among students amongst others. The study is congruent with Jin (2020), who posited that behavioral counseling is effective at reducing STI transmission in those at higher risk, reducing STI acquisition by as much as 30%.

Findings from table 2 revealed the mean responses on the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce the spread of sexually transmitted diseases. The finding showed that exposing students to healthy protective sexual behaviours in counselling can reduce the risk of STD spreads among students, educating students on how STDs are contacted would help identify risk of sexually transmitted diseases, providing enlightenment on the need to use condoms during sex would reduce the spread of STDs amongst others. The study also discovered that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of counsellors and students on the extent risk reduction counselling strategies would reduce spread of sexually transmitted diseases among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings relate with WHO (2006), observing that when young adults are also exposed to diverse risks of sexually transmitted diseases transecting different levels of causation, their could be significant reduction in the spread of the disease.

Lastly, the findings on research question 3 as revealed in table 3 showed that at high extent preventive counselling strategy would reduce the spread of sexually transmitted diseases among secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings showed that to a high extent exposing students to preventive measures to sexually transmitted diseases, enlightening young adolescent on the prevalence of sexually transmitted diseases in the area, promoting safer sexual practices through counselling programmes in schools can reduce the spread of STDs. The findings relates with Oluwole et al., (2020) asserted

that comprehensive sexuality education, STI and HIV pre- and post-test counselling, condom promotion and interventions targeted at key populations are preventive counselling measures geared towards reducing the spread of sexually transmitted Diseases.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that counselling is an effective means for reducing the spread of sexually transmitted diseases among youngsters in secondary schools. Specifically, the utilization of behavioural counselling, risk reduction counselling and preventive counselling are identified as the strategies that can help reduce the spread of sexually transmitted diseases at high extent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that;

1. School administrators encourage guidance counsellors in organization of counselling programmes that are tailored towards discouraging unhealthy sexual behaviours of students. This can help students develop a healthy sexual culture thereby reducing their vulnerability to sexually transmitted diseases
2. Guidance counsellors should provide orientation for students on the risks of sexually transmitted diseases in their immediate environment. This orientation will help reduce the risk of sexually transmitted diseases among secondary school students.
3. Encouraging students to confide in guidance counsellors regarding their sexual lifestyle can help enhance preventive counselling in secondary schools. Counsellors will be able to provide guidance for students for proper avoidance situations leading to contact of sexually transmitted diseases.

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